

MICROSTRUCTURE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CMC MANUFACTURED VIA THE LIQUID PHASE ROUTE

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ABSTRACT

An alternative technology is presently under development to produce CMC structures with lower costs and shorter manufacturing times. The process is based on the infiltration of liquid silicon into porous carbon/carbon resulting in C/C-SiC materials with an internal oxidation protection of the load carrying fibres. The selection of suitable fibres and precursors, the formation of crack pattern and their dependance on fibre/matrix bondings as well as the conditions for an adequate silicon infiltration are described in detail. Fabricated and tested C/C-SiC components indicate that the achieved properties are also valid for complex structures.

Keywords: CMC, C/C-SiC, liquid silicon infiltration, microstructure, capillary

1. INTRODUCTION

CMC materials development has only been realised on an industrial scale by the isothermal CVI process [1]. However, manufacturing takes several weeks to months and costs are very high. Economic production on larger scale for civil applications is therefore not feasible. The in-house developed process of silicon infiltration of C/C composites with subsequent chemical reaction enables a short processing time. It allows a component production period of about two weeks and is based on three manufacturing steps: CFRP shaping, pyrolysis and silicon infiltration [2, 3, 4].

As precursors, one-part thermoset systems are used to fabricate laminates with 2D-reinforcements. Common techniques for reinforcing polymers by continuous carbon fabrics have been adapted to the curing cycle of the precursors. By resin transfer moulding (RTM) as well as autoclave technology flat plates, tubes and structural components have been manufactured. Generally, the autoclave process will be preferred for large spherical shaped components with 2D-fibre reinforcement, whereas more integrated structures with 3D-fibre skeletons are manufactured by RTM.

During pyrolysis (900°C) the matrix adopts a crack pattern as a result of the precursor shrinkage and induced forces by the stiffer fibres. To maintain the shape and geometry in a one-step pyrolysis the furnace heating rates must be low (3-5 K/h) within the critical range of the highest matrix mass loss, which controls the duration of this thermal process. After pyrolysis, the composites show a crack pattern with translaminar channels resulting in an open porosity of about 20%.

During the subsequent siliconizing process (1550°C) one takes advantage of the low viscosity of silicon and its high reactivity with carbon. To prevent chemical attack on the fibres they must be protected by coatings or by suitable fibre arrangements. As the very expensive fibre coating counteracts the low cost goals of the process, the work is focused on the development of controlled crack systems with dense C/C regions of high fibre content and continuous channels between them. Within these channels the liquid silicon infiltrates the C/C-composite very fast driven by capillary forces and the subsequent exothermal reaction with matrix carbon leads to the cracks being filled by SiC. The key points of the manufactured C/C-SiC are the protection of load carrying carbon/carbon areas by silicon carbide to increase the oxidation resistance, while maintaining the high damage tolerance of C/C.

2. FORMATION OF THE MICROSTRUCTURE

As for all CMC materials there exists a direct correlation between the fibre/matrix interface, the microstructure and the mechanical behaviour. In the case of this process, the properties of C/C-SiC materials are primarily dominated by the crack pattern before siliconizing. Therefore, the influence of fibre type, precursor shrinkage and the fibre/matrix interface have been examined.

2.1. Fibre stability

The maximum temperature of this process is considerably higher than in the CVI-process. During siliconizing, the C/C components have to withstand temperatures of up to 1550°C for about one hour. Thus, only thermally stable fibres are suitable for this process. Commercially available PAN-based fibres of different types have been evaluated for their thermal stability under real processing conditions. Fibre bundle tests were carried out with HT fibres (T300), IM fibres (T800), and HM fibres (M40). The strength values after pyrolysis at 900°C and 1550°C were evaluated by Weibull analysis and compared with untreated fibres (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Fibre degradation under fabrication conditions

T300 fibres show the lowest decrease in strength but remain on a low level. Although M40 fibres are very stable, the highest residual strength was measured with T800 fibres. These results in production furnaces correspond well with tests in inert atmosphere (Fig. 2). Fibre bundles of the same types were treated for 1, 10 and 100h in nitrogen and tested after the heat treatment. As a result, the influence of temperature on strength level is more pronounced than the time of exposure. Summarising these results, the T800 fibre seems to be the most suitable fibre for this process.

Figure 2: Residual bundle strength for different fibre types after heat treatment in inert atmosphere

2.2. Char yield and shrinkage of the precursor

The main requirements for a good polymer precursor material are low price, low viscosity before curing, high char yield and sufficient mechanical properties after pyrolysis. In a screening test the thermosetting resin XP-60 was chosen as the standard precursor for C/C skeletons because of its extremely low viscosity (10-20 mPa.s) and its high char yield of 61% after pyrolysis at 1550°C (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: TG analysis of XP-60

The rearrangement of the molecular chains causes a volumetric shrinkage of the neat resin of about 50% combined with an increase of density from 1.14g/cm³ to 1.4g/cm³ (Table 1).

Pyrolysis temp. °C	Char yield %	Shrinkage %		Density g/cm ³
		longitudinal	volumetric	
900	64	19.5	48	1.40
1550	61	20.5	50	1.39

Table 1: Char yield and shrinkage of XP-60

Due to the high char yield the residual stresses are low and a nearly void free glassy carbon is created. However, when embedding carbon fibres into the resin the shrinkage impediment causes

high stresses in the matrix and changes its microstructure. In direction parallel to the fibres the matrix shrinkage is restrained and leads to translaminar cracks in the C/C-laminate. The formation of this crack pattern is dependent on the fibre type, the weaving mode and the fibre/matrix bonding forces.

2.3. The role of fibre/matrix bonding

The matrix shrinkage during pyrolysis leads in the case of fabric reinforcement to a segmentation of the fibre bundles, creating transverse cracks around dense C/C areas. If the bonding forces between fibre and matrix are strong, eg because of high amounts of active surface groups, the shrinkage stresses are high and the crack pattern is coarse. The resultant C/C morphology allows good infiltration, but the failure behaviour of the C/C-SiC composite is brittle (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: SEM micrograph and failure behaviour of C/C-SiC with high fibre/matrix bonding (bright: SiC, dark: segments of fibre bundles)

To increase fracture toughness fibre pull out effects within the bundles must be achieved. Therefore, the adhesion between fibres and the XP-60 matrix has to be reduced in the polymer stage. Different thermal pretreatments in nitrogen have been carried out and their influence on microstructure and mechanical behaviour were examined (Fig. 5). However, too low bondings lead to a complete shrinking away of the matrix from the fibres after pyrolysis, so that the porous matrix can cause heavy attack of silicon on the exposed fibres, resulting in poor C/C-SiC properties. The compromise between internal protection and damage tolerance behaviour lies in an intermediate fibre/matrix bonding which allows inter fibre gliding inside the fibre bundles.

Figure 5: Influence of fibre/matrix bonding (FMB) on the failure behaviour of C/C-SiC (fibre: M40)

3. THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF LIQUID SILICON INFILTRATION

3.1. General aspects

For numerical simulation of the infiltration process, an adequate simulation model has been developed. The microstructure of the porous carbon/carbon preform is of great influence on the infiltration dynamics with liquid silicon. Presupposing the C/C morphology with translaminar in-plane channels, the infiltration can be well described by capillary laws. Since infiltration velocity is very high, the filling of the open porosity with liquid silicon and the chemical reaction $C + Si \rightarrow SiC$ can be investigated separately.

3.2. Maximum infiltration height

Using an intermediate capillary diameter d_K the maximum infiltration height h_{max} of porous carbon/carbon structures can be described by the following equation:

$$h_{max} = \frac{4 \cdot \sigma \cdot \cos \vartheta}{\rho_{Si} \cdot g} \cdot \frac{1}{d_K}$$

Since they are of great influence on the infiltration dynamics, many investigations in the literature have been carried out to determine the properties of molten silicon (Table 2). For the in-house manufactured porous carbon/carbon material with intermediate capillary diameters of $d_K = 10$ to $30 \mu m$, the theoretical infiltration height lies between 5 to 1.5m (Fig. 6). Therefore, large components can be infiltrated and the dimensions of resulting C/SiC-structures are only limited by the geometry of the heating facilities .

Density	ρ	g/cm ³	2.33 - 2.34 (20°C) 2.53 - 2.55 (1420°)
Melting point	T	°C	1414 - 1420
Surface stress vs. vacuum	σ	N/m	0.72 - 0.75 (1550°C)
Wetting angle	ϑ	°	30 -41 (vs. SiC/Vacuum) 0 - 22 (vs. C/Vacuum)
Dynamic viscosity	η	Pa·s	5.10 - 7.65·10 ⁻⁴ (1440°C) 4.59 - 6.38·10 ⁻⁴ (1560°C)

Table 2: Properties of Silicon [6]

Figure 6: Theoretical infiltration height of porous carbon/carbon structures

3.3. Impregnation dynamics

The impregnation dynamics of translaminar capillary channels by molten silicon can be described by the nonlinear differential equation for $h(t)$

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = \frac{d_k^2}{32\eta \cdot v_w^2 \cdot h} \cdot \left(\frac{4\sigma \cdot \cos \vartheta}{d_k} - \rho \cdot g \cdot h \right)$$

where v_w represents the tortuosity coefficient or the curvature factor of the capillary channels.

The numerical integration of this equation is shown in Figure 7 up to an infiltration height of about 600mm. Smaller capillary diameters result in higher mounting heights but due to a decrease in volume flow, there is an increase in impregnation time. However, most structures are completely infiltrated within less than one minute.

Figure 7: Infiltration characteristics of porous carbon/carbon structures

3.4. Chemical reaction

The first contact of molten Si with carbon leads to the immediate formation of SiC-layers at the capillary walls [7]. Due to this fact the reaction velocity of the formation of further SiC is controlled by the diffusion of Si atoms through the SiC layer into the carbon.

In the ideal case the infiltrated liquid silicon only reacts with the matrix-carbon of the porous C/C-structure, whereas the carbon fibers remain unchanged. This simplification is true for most cases, in which the dense carbon fiber bundles are surrounded by a layer of glassy carbon.

Figure 8 shows that the fibre volume content φ_F of the porous carbon/carbon preform has a great influence on the phase ratios of SiC and C in the matrix of the C/C-SiC material. The manufactured C/C-SiC shows typical mass ratios of about 33% of SiC and about 67% of C. Assuming stoichiometrical reaction, the simulation model is in good correspondence with experimental results.

Figure 8: Theoretical mass ratios of C/C-SiC material

4. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE C/C-SiC COMPOSITE

Mechanical and thermal tests have been carried out with flat samples and tubes ($\varnothing 28$ and 68mm) within the Institute's collaboration in the Sonderforschungsbereich [5]. The specimens consist of bidirectionally reinforced C/C-SiC with usually as-received HT fibres (T300, HTA). Generally, the failure mode is brittle and the residual strength potential of the fibres (see 2.1.) is only partially utilized in the composite. The characteristic properties of state-of-the-art C/C-SiC material are summarized in Table 3.

Tensile strength	MPa	90 - 115
Elongation at break	%	0.23
Young's modulus	GPa	60 - 70
Poisson's ratio		0.2 - 0.22
Compression strength	MPa	300
Flexure strength	MPa	160 - 200
Shear strength	MPa	55 - 60
Open porosity	%	3 - 7
Fibre content	Vol. %	55 - 65
Density	g/cm ³	1.8 - 1.95
Max. temperature of application	°C	1600 - 1800
Total emmissivity (1000-1750°C)		0.65 - 0.75
Thermal expansion		
• parallel (RT-1500°C)	1/K	1 - 2·10 ⁻⁶
• normal (RT-1500°C)	1/K	4 - 6·10 ⁻⁶
Thermal conductivity		
• parallel (200-1700°C)	W/mK	10 - 15
• normal (200-1700°C)	W/mK	6 - 8
Spec. heat capacity (200-1700°C)	J/kgK	1150 - 1850

Table 3: Typical RT-properties of 2D C/C-SiC

Besides these static values which show the basis for further improvements, the material can be characterized by the following statements:

- Low cycle fatigue tests (LCF) showed an increase in strength of about 20% after 10^7 cycles accompanied by a decrease in stiffness of about 12%.
- There is no significant difference between sample strength and the corresponding stress level in structural components. Specimens, cut from complex components, show identical mechanical properties to those in Table 3.
- The standard deviation within one material batch is below 10%. Nevertheless, manufacturing conditions greatly influence the mechanical properties.
- Plasma channel tests and real reentry tests in capsules demonstrate the excellent thermoshock resistance of C/C-SiC ($> 1000^\circ\text{C}/\text{sec}$).
- The oxidative stability of C/C-SiC is considerably higher than that of C/C. CVD-SiC multilayers as external coatings are compatible and increase the thermal resistance primarily at the free edges.
- C/C-SiC shows superior properties for brake disk applications. The values of wear and oxidation are low, the coefficient of friction is constant over a wide temperature range and the material shows a good behaviour under wet conditions.

5. APPLICATIONS

Besides the Institute's activities on tribological applications (brake development, materials for bearings) the applicability of C/C-SiC is also under investigation for structures of ballistic capsules and winged spacecrafts. Two C/C-SiC samples, embedded in the ablator, have successfully demonstrated their resistance against extreme heat fluxes during the reentry of the Russian Foton 8 capsule. For the German Express capsule a C/C-SiC tile will partly replace the standard ablation structure.

Within the Hypersonic Technology Programme the Institute is involved in designing, manufacturing and testing a structural component as an alternative to an industrially developed component for an intake flap of the propulsion system. A multi spar component of $270 \times 270 \times 35 \text{mm}^3$ (Fig. 9) has been manufactured via the liquid infiltration process. As it is designed in a near-net-shape technology, no joints and no interruption of load carrying fibres are characteristics of the design concept.

Figure 9: C/C-SiC intake flap in the preliminary CFRP stage

6. CONCLUSIONS

C/C-SiC material with 2D reinforcement has been developed by the infiltration of liquid silicon into porous C/C. The total processing time including preforming and matrix conversion amounts to about two weeks. The state-of-the-art process allows a high flexibility in design and manufacturing of materials with moderate strength levels. The key points for higher strength lie in an appropriate fibre/matrix interface. The still too high bonding forces must be reduced by fibre pretreatments and the adaptation of the C/C microstructure. The infiltration dynamics of silicon allow the manufacture of C/C-SiC components on an industrial scale. Structural parts have already been realised and tested as limited life structures over short times at high temperatures.

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